

Comparative table for evaluation experiments of Information Retrieval Systems.

Test name	Scope of the study	Methodology	Result	Limitations	Pathbreaking Approach
Cranfield 1	Aimed to assess and critically analyse various manual indexing methods for small information retrieval systems.	The efficacy of manually assigned indexing terms was rigorously tested by using a controlled dataset.	Concluded that systematic indexing produced better retrieval accuracy.	Small datasets and lacked diversity in test collections.	Pioneered evaluation of indexing techniques; laid groundwork for IR evaluation.
Cranfield 2	The objective was to assess the performance of the system, specifically focusing on retrieval techniques.	Introduced test collections, relevance judgments, and precision/recall measures.	Established precision and recall as standard IR performance measures.	Results were specific to the dataset; limited generalizability.	Introduced precision and recall metrics; established reusable test collections.
MEDLARS	Focused on establishing a medical literature retrieval system for biomedical research.	Created a bibliographic retrieval system for medical articles with MeSH indexing.	Successfully retrieved relevant medical articles; supported clinical needs.	Limited to biomedical literature; less applicable outside of healthcare.	Pioneered domain-specific retrieval systems for healthcare; influencing future specialized databases.

SMART	Evaluation of the effectiveness of many different types of analysis and search procedures.	Focused on experimentation with automated indexing, ranking algorithms, vector space models and query matching.	Proved the efficiency of vector space models for ranking documents.	Focused on academic experiments; lacked scalability for large-scale systems.	Innovated the use of vector space models and ranking algorithms.
STAIRS	Focused on developing a corporate information retrieval system for business contexts.	Evaluated query performance in structured and semi-structured business data.	Showed structured data retrieval was faster and more accurate than unstructured approaches.	Lack of scalability to unstructured data; heavily dependent on metadata quality.	Highlighted the importance of structured data and metadata in corporate IR systems.
TREC	Designed for large scale assessment of text retrieval systems using real-world datasets.	Used standardized test collections and annual tasks for benchmarking.	Established benchmarks for large-scale IR; fostering innovation in algorithms.	Computationally expensive; biased toward high-resource participants.	Enabled benchmarking for modern large-scale IR systems; inspired diverse participation.